

Research Article

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The role of immersive technologies in K-12 education

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Abstract: The rapid adoption of immersive technologies such as virtual and augmented reality opens new perspectives for teaching and learning in schools. Particularly within the digitalisation of education systems, these technologies are gaining relevance. They function as potentially transformative tools for learning and for creating inclusive educational spaces. This article examines the use of immersive technologies in K-12 education with the goal of illuminating didactic design possibilities, technical challenges, and ethical as well as inclusion-related questions. The authors, an interdisciplinary team of experts in technology,

didactics, and inclusive education, employed a scenario-based methodology. Guided by a values-driven consensus process, the team crafted a future scenario that makes the use of immersive technologies in the school context tangible and serves as a basis for deriving concrete measures. The resulting contribution is structured into six fields of action that specify requirements for didactic integration, inclusive access, interoperable infrastructures, standards, and teacher professionalization. The findings are linked to current empirical research debates. Such projections are inherently limited, especially given dynamic technological developments and heterogeneous school contexts. Nonetheless, the article offers a conceptual framework and practice-oriented recommendations that aim to support the reflective and responsible integration of immersive technologies in schools, embedding inclusive principles throughout.

Keywords: immersive technologies; virtual reality; augmented reality; K-12 education; inclusion; educational innovation

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1 Immersive technologies in today's K-12 education

The rapid development of immersive technologies, such as Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and XR (with “X” serving as a placeholder for various forms), is opening up new opportunities for school education. Here, immersion is understood as a technological characteristic that describes the extent to which a computer system can create the illusion of an environment for the user's senses.¹

Immersive technologies offer significant advantages for school education. They increase students' motivation and engagement by fostering attention through interactive and lifelike experiences.^{2–4} Particularly in subjects like science or history, they can make complex or abstract concepts, such as molecular structures or historical events, more tangible and easier to understand.^{2–6} A key potential lies in promoting inclusion through digital education.⁷ Due to their adaptability, VR and AR systems can

accommodate individual needs (e.g., personalized learning pace), support diverse learning pathways, and improve access to education for all students.^{4,8} Qualitative research in inclusive school settings supports these benefits. Such research demonstrates that immersive VR can provide safe, individualized learning environments that stimulate imagination, encourage expression and communication, and enable students with intellectual disabilities and autism to develop skills transferable to real-world contexts.⁹ However, systematic reviews reveal that implementation remains limited in scope, with research focusing predominantly on specific disability groups rather than universal approaches.¹⁰ This narrow focus risks reinforcing compensatory rather than preventive approaches to inclusion. When technologies are designed for specific user groups rather than following universal design principles, learners outside these groups face additional barriers, and educators must rely on assistive technologies that often suffer from poor usability, high costs, and limited availability.⁷ Preliminary design guidelines grounded in Universal Design for Learning are now emerging to address this challenge, offering a foundation for Virtual Reality Learning Applications (VRLAs) that systematically accommodate diverse learner needs from the outset.¹¹ Additionally, VR applications promote experimental and practical learning by enabling safe simulations of complex concepts in virtual environments.^{6,8,12} Studies further show that VR learning environments enhance knowledge retention over the long term and foster action-oriented learning.^{6,8,13} Another major advantage is the ability to strengthen social learning. Virtual environments encourage collaboration and interaction among students, fostering teamwork and social skills.^{2,5}

Despite this potential, there are also significant challenges. Health and ethical concerns, such as potential eye strain, dizziness, or data privacy issues, raise important questions.^{2,4,14–17} Additionally, schools often face technical barriers, including complex operating systems or a lack of compatibility between technologies.^{2,3,5,6,17} Another obstacle is the lack of didactic concepts and high-quality educational content specifically developed for school contexts.^{5,6,8,14,17} Teacher competency development is also a critical factor.^{2–5,17} To use immersive technologies effectively, teachers require extensive training and continuous professional development. Furthermore, the high acquisition and maintenance costs of necessary hardware pose a significant barrier to widespread implementation.^{2,3,5,17} Another issue concerns the evaluation of learning outcomes. Clear standards for objectively measuring the success of VR-supported environments are lacking.¹⁴ For the

German school context, a consolidated account of VR potentials, limitations, and implementation requirements has been provided in prior work.¹⁷

Against this backdrop, the article aims to identify the main potentials and challenges of immersive technologies in schools and to reflect on them across three core fields of action:

1. Technological developments
2. Didactic design
3. Inclusive education (transversal theme)

These fields address different, yet interrelated, levels of school practice.

Rather than focusing on short-term hardware trends, the technological perspective focuses on software standards, interfaces and platform structures that enable long-term, low-barrier learning environments. The didactic design perspective discusses how immersive technologies can be meaningfully embedded in the curriculum through motivating, action-oriented learning formats. Inclusive education permeates both areas as a normative guiding principle, with attention to equitable access, personalization and pedagogical responsibility.

Methodologically, the article builds on a values-driven, scenario-based approach carried out in interdisciplinary groups involving experts from school practice, research and development. The scenario that emerged structures the central challenges and options for action and provides the foundation for concrete recommendations that are anchored in current research.

2 Methodology

The future perspectives presented in this paper were developed through an interdisciplinary, scenario-based foresight process. They were shaped by experts in technological development, didactic design, and inclusive education. Importantly, the article is not an empirical study in the sense of systematically collecting and analyzing participant data to test hypotheses. Instead, it follows a normatively oriented scenario approach: the central aim is to construct a well-grounded, vivid, and value-driven vision that can serve as an impulse for shaping future school education with immersive technologies. Accordingly, the primary data basis of the process consists of collaboratively produced workshop artefacts (e.g., structured notes, visual mappings, and consolidated statements), as well as iterative consensus building across the expert groups.

2.1 Analysis conducted by experts in three focus groups

In the first step, three thematically focused expert groups were formed, each corresponding to one of the central fields of action. Within their respective groups, the experts articulated grounded development perspectives for three time horizons (10, 25, and 50 years) in their own domains.

Inclusive education was not treated as an isolated topic but as a transversal principle that permeated all other considerations. This decision reflects the particular relevance of inclusion to school education. Immersive technologies can contribute to greater educational equity; however, if implemented without reflection, they may reinforce existing social and digital inequalities.

Consequently, inclusive education was systematically embedded in the deliberations of the other two groups, for instance, through questions concerning accessible technologies and differentiation-sensitive didactic design.

Across the expert meetings, the work was organized as interdisciplinary deliberation rather than as formal data collection. Within and across the focus groups, participants collaboratively externalized assumptions, needs, and constraints using complementary brainstorming and visualization methods, primarily facilitated through shared Miro boards. The boards served as a common workspace to collect ideas, cluster them thematically, and iteratively refine formulations (e.g., for values, plausible boundary conditions, and actionable requirements). To move from divergence to convergence, intermediate syntheses were created between meetings. A small interdisciplinary subset of participants prepared discussion materials (e.g., clustered maps and preliminary formulations) which were then brought back into the subsequent plenary discussion with all involved experts. Decisions and refinements were documented directly in the shared workspace and consolidated stepwise into the value set, the scenario narrative, and the subsequent fields of action.

2.2 Value-driven alignment

Because the aim of the scenario process was not to describe the most probable futures but to formulate a positive, actionable one, a second step introduced a values-oriented framework. In other words, the scenario is not intended as a forecast, but as a normative and action-oriented vision that remains plausible and realistic enough within the chosen time horizon. Since specific developments can be judged differently from the various perspectives, a shared normative basis was needed to establish a common understanding of a desirable future.

Each of the three groups therefore identified key values that, in their view, should underpin desirable developments in their respective fields of action. Values such as participation, inclusion, personalization, open access and interdisciplinarity were then discussed across groups, critically examined and consolidated. The resulting set of shared educational values provided the normative foundation for the subsequent scenario development.

2.3 Scenario development using a normative scenario technique

For the creation of vivid future visions, the scenario technique was chosen as the methodological instrument. Our approach follows the typology proposed by van Notten et al.,¹⁸ which classifies scenarios along three dimensions:

- **Project goal:** The scenario process is normative because it formulates a desirable objective for school education with immersive technologies.
- **Process design:** The approach is intuitive; it rests on discursive, creative group processes and specialist expertise.
- **Scenario content:** The scenarios are qualitative; they rely on narrative descriptions rather than quantitative modelling.

The scenario developed on this basis relates to the year 2035. The choice of this time horizon is based on several considerations. On the one hand, it is practical and compatible with existing systems, since many educational policy measures in areas such as curriculum development, teacher education, or technical equipment are designed for 5- to 10-year periods. Additionally, the year 2035 offers a sufficiently broad timeframe to open up visionary design spaces without methodologically sliding into speculative long-term forecasts. The combination of concreteness and creative freedom makes the scenario both actionable and narratively effective.

While preparing the scenario, the expert groups also considered broader development perspectives (25 and 50 years). However, the 10-year horizon was chosen as the focus of this article to reduce reliance on far-reaching assumptions. Beyond a decade, infrastructures, governance, and socio-technical adoption dynamics would have dominated the discussion and weakened the robustness of an “informed vision”. The 2035 horizon therefore represents a compromise: sufficiently forward-looking yet still allowing a comparatively realistic assessment of what could be shaped within existing educational and policy cycles.

In terms of content, an exploratory-analytical approach was chosen that considers both best-case and worst-case

aspects. Since many potentially problematic developments, such as data misuse, platform monopolization, or digital exclusion, do not arise specifically from XR technologies, but rather represent systemic digital challenges, the development of an independent dystopian scenario was foregone. Instead, a positive scenario is at the center that designs a realistic and at the same time desirable future vision for everyday school life with immersive technologies. The negative potentials are named and discussed in contrast to this in order to make areas of tension visible and to highlight the areas where action is needed.

2.4 Deriving concrete courses of action

In the final step, concrete measures and recommendations were formulated to support successful school use of immersive technologies within the chosen 10-year horizon. These measures were co-developed across all working groups, iteratively discussed, and consolidated collectively. The scenario narrative does not function as the analytical source from which measures were derived; rather, it serves as a boundary object that makes the targeted horizon tangible and helps readers to understand how the various requirements and constraints come together in a coherent future classroom. The measures are therefore grounded in the cross-group synthesis of expert deliberations and aligned with the shared value basis, while being structured along overarching themes (e.g., didactic guidelines and teaching principles, open XR infrastructures and OER ecosystems¹, standards and guidelines for data protection and accessibility).

The following chapters present the results of this methodical approach: the consolidated value basis, the developed future scenario, and the thematically structured courses of action.

3 Shared values as the foundation for scenario development

The goal of the scenario process does not lie in describing probable futures, but rather in formulating a positive, actionable future based on values shared by the authors. The following values form the normative foundation for scenario development in the subsequent process. They should

be understood as a whole and are not hierarchically structured.

1. **Equal Opportunities & Participation:** The principle of equal educational opportunities for all people underlies this paper. The participation of all students in the learning process serves as a guiding principle, regardless of their individual needs or abilities. Social and digital inequality should be actively addressed. Active participation by learners should take place throughout the entire process to foster students' sense of self-efficacy. Learners should help shape the learning process and be involved in developing XR applications. However, application development should not only involve active users but should also include teachers and all other stakeholders in the process.
2. **Embodied & Experience-Based Learning:** When XR is understood as an educational medium, the focus is directed toward learning processes in, through, and with XR. Using XR means that the body becomes central to learning processes and interaction occurs with both virtual and physical reality. This shows that learning happens in an embodied way and is connected to cognitive processes. Learners thus experience learning content directly and through hands-on activities.
3. **Inclusion & Accessibility:** While equal education for all people excludes no one by definition, there is particular emphasis on inclusive practices, which are outlined explicitly here. Learning environments should be designed at both technological and didactic levels to be accessible and usable for everyone. User-specific adaptation options should be considered essential. Application design should focus on creating multimodal experiences that engage multiple senses and open up new possibilities for learning and discovery.
4. **Personalization & Adaptivity:** Information can be experienced through various sensory channels and adapted to individual needs. This adaptivity enables personalization of the learning process. However, this should not be understood as learning that fundamentally takes place alone and individually. Rather, it involves collaborative learning where information can be adapted and modified across different sensory channels for each participant. This approach creates personalized learning experiences while simultaneously enabling shared learning among students. Both teachers and learners share responsibility for this process, which is supported by data collection and analysis. When data use complies with all legal and ethical requirements, learning analytics can effectively enhance the learning process.

¹ Open Educational Resources (OER) are teaching, learning, and research materials that are freely accessible and openly licensed. An OER ecosystem refers to the broader socio-technical environment that enables the creation, adaptation, distribution, and sustainable use of OER.

5. **Open Access** Content developed for use with XR technologies should be made available to the general public as Open Educational Resources and thus be adaptable for specific target groups.
6. **Acceptance of XR as Educational Medium & Evidence-Based Research:** XR technology should be understood as an educational medium by participating stakeholders and society at large. To achieve this, it is essential to accompany the processes of implementation, exploration, and application from the outset through interdisciplinary research. Evidence-based, interdisciplinary research drawing from fields such as computer science, media studies, subject-specific didactics, pedagogy, general didactics and philosophy should analyze and illuminate the potentials and limitations within this dynamic field.

4 A school day with XR in 2035

During the first lesson, the high school student Luca stands on the schoolyard wearing her XR headset, examining the half-finished digital model of a bridge. For Luca, wearing the XR device and seeing virtual objects embedded in the real world feels entirely natural and unremarkable, just like another part of her everyday school routine. She's working on her project for an interdisciplinary science class. With a hand gesture, she reinforces a steel beam and starts a load test of the bridge. The AI-powered learning environment has automatically suggested suitable bridge models, materials, and physical parameters based on her progress so far. At the same time, the system analyzes where Luca needs support. This creates a personalized learning environment that's embedded within collaborative work. On the schoolyard grass, her concrete and steel structure shimmers in the sunlight. The load test shows how the weight of a virtual train distributes across the bridge. "Almost perfect," she murmurs as the visualization shows it sagging slightly. In class, they learned that even the smallest deformations provide clues about material choices. She loves these kinds of details, especially when she can test what works directly, like today in her STEM project, without anything actually breaking.

Alex, who actually prefers teaching languages over science, watches the scene from his spot. He was initially skeptical when the school began integrating XR technologies into teaching. He had never considered himself particularly tech-savvy. But now he appreciates the virtual dashboard on his headset that shows him in real time who needs support, who has already uploaded results, and who might be spending too long on a task. In the past, he would have had

to supervise multiple groups simultaneously without any overview. Now he gets hints about where his help is really needed, without anyone in the class being singled out.

All students use XR devices that they borrow on a long-term basis from their school's media library. The devices are adapted to their personal needs, including eye distance, weight, and fit. Despite these differences between devices, they remain fully compatible with the learning environment and provide content thanks to open standards. This content comes from a publicly organized educational cloud, without dependencies on individual vendors. Alex feels relieved that his students bring their own devices, as they can set up and adjust their XR headset to suit their individual needs independently. He is delighted that his students are becoming tech-savvy.

During the sixth lesson, Luca and Alex meet again in history class, and the classroom transforms. The desks don't disappear, but through the XR headsets they become stalls in a bustling medieval marketplace. Alex uses a free application from an educational cloud that he has specifically adapted for this lesson. The marketplace environment corresponds to historical views of the old town near their school, letting students travel back in time to their own city's past. Luca, who usually struggles to get excited about history, has transformed herself today into a young merchant wearing traditional clothing that she digitally assembled herself. Next to her, classmates sell spices, fish, or ceramics. The marketplace is filled with AI-controlled characters that Luca can talk to. An elderly woman explains something about medieval social structure to her, while a child demonstrates the rules of an old dice game.

The marketplace can be revisited at any time, enabling targeted repetition and practice situations, even outside school hours. Through the haptic gloves Luca wears, she feels the rough material when she picks up a clay jug. A side-mounted scent sensor simulates smells – she smells dried herbs mixed with the aromas of freshly baked goods.

What Luca particularly likes is that she can decide how much she perceives at once. A small menu on her wrist lets her adjust everything: ambient sounds, subtitles, simple language mode, or whether NPCs use sign language automatically. For Luca, this is simply how learning works: she knows that everyone tailors the environment to their own needs and preferences. Today she has turned down the ambient sounds, since she sometimes gets overwhelmed by too many voices. As she walks through the market, she notices a classmate using sign language with a merchant nearby. When she focuses on them, the learning environment provides a live translation, according to the settings she chose for herself.

When she sees a fierce watchdog at a jewelry merchant's stall, she pauses briefly. Nearby she spots her classmate Peter. His presence shows up in her interface as an active learning partner. She remembers that he has a great fear of dogs. But to her surprise, he waves briefly and says, "I didn't completely hide the dog this time – it's just a silhouette for me. That's manageable. I want to know what the merchant says about the craft guilds." Luca smiles. For her, such moments of exchange and mutual consideration are naturally part of learning. Together, they consider whether to include a scene from this later in their portfolio. Then they say goodbye again. Each returns to their own learning experience, but never completely alone.

Alex has gotten used to the new technology. An AI-supported analysis tool discreetly warns him if someone ignores content for too long or feels uncomfortable. Data protection and transparency are carefully maintained. Every access remains traceable and viewable. He observes through his interface who is where in the market. When someone gets stuck, he can join directly as a quiet observer or active supporter. He appreciates being able to provide more personalized and targeted support to students this way, without abandoning his role as teacher for the rest of the class. For Alex it is a tremendous relief that students customize their own preferences and are able to adjust the learning environment to their own needs. This allows him more time to give individual support, without getting caught up in troubleshooting inaccessible technology.

At the end of the day, Luca has not only nearly finished building her bridge but also created a digital diary entry about market day in her medieval city. Both are transferred to her learning portfolio. The technology she uses feels completely natural to her. Luca disinfects her headset with a hygiene wipe, thinking to herself that it's a tool that simply works and has truly changed the way she learns.

5 Turning points – measures for shaping a positive future

The preceding scenario shows how education with immersive media could be designed: technologically integrated, didactically grounded, and conceived with inclusion in mind. To enable such developments in the education system, targeted measures are needed across several interconnected areas. The following six areas outline key starting points.

Several of the measures outlined below are not purely speculative, but build on existing research findings, pilot projects, and already available technological developments.

Where appropriate, references to current research or practical implementations are provided to illustrate that parts of the envisioned future are already emerging today. At the same time, these examples are not presented as blueprints, but as indicative starting points that require further didactic, technical, and organizational adaptation for school contexts.

5.1 Developing didactic guidelines & teaching principles for XR

To achieve this best-case scenario, schools need comprehensive guidelines for XR use that operate at both didactic and content levels. These guidelines must address structural considerations like space and time requirements and general organizational approaches for XR lessons. They also need to tackle broader content questions, including technology-critical reflections that help determine what experiences to show students and what to avoid. Additionally, these guidelines should establish fundamental principles for managing sensory input and limiting usage times, providing a clear framework for preventing potential cognitive overload in students. These design principles align with findings from recent research on immersive learning environments, which highlight the importance of didactic structuring, adaptive support, and reflection phases for sustainable learning outcomes.

Scenarios for adaptive, repeatable, and differentiated XR use should be created, published, and implemented. A central part of this process involves continuously developing knowledge about which content can be effectively addressed through XR and how to design these experiences. This should particularly include integrating multi-sensory content such as smells, haptics, and sound, along with options for adaptation. When creating these scenarios, inclusive avatar design is essential. This means avoiding stereotypical representations while offering adaptable non-verbal communication options like gestures, facial expressions, and pointing tools, as well as various levels of avatar abstraction to support diverse communication styles and expression preferences.

For the history teacher Alex in the presented scenario to have the capacity for individual learning support, designing lessons with XR authoring systems is beneficial. This allows teachers to access different modules during both planning and implementation. Here too, adaptivity plays a central role in the didactic reconstruction of subject matter, both in how the authoring systems are designed and in how learners interact with the system.

The virtual marketplace enables a shared experience that can be used by multiple students simultaneously while

still being personalized for individual needs. To achieve this, technical development and didactic scenarios should prioritize designs that are inherently built for multiplayer use.

Important design considerations include working with NPCs, AI agents, and historical/cultural representations, as well as creating opportunities for students to shift perspectives. These considerations are significant because they function on two levels: they serve as actual content that students learn about, while simultaneously providing the structural framework for how that learning takes place.

5.2 Building open XR infrastructures & OER ecosystems

To ensure that education with immersive media remains permanently accessible to the public and pedagogically adaptable, targeted measures are needed to build open XR infrastructures and OER ecosystems. The educational cloud depicted in the scenario, from which Luca can access content as needed, will not emerge automatically but requires coordinated development, strategic support, and collaborative implementation.

A central step involves expanding existing OER platforms (infrastructures that host, curate, and provide access to OERs, supporting their discovery, reuse, adaptation, and redistribution) to include XR-capable content. This requires standardized interfaces, legally secure media licensing models, and accessible delivery formats. In parallel, cross-platform app repositories for immersive educational content should be built that remain accessible regardless of the device being used. Integrating this content into school systems requires binding compatibility and quality standards. Similar challenges and potentials have already been identified in current discussions on OER ecosystems and platform-based educational infrastructures, indicating that XR-specific developments can build on existing structures rather than starting from scratch.

Another key area involves developing intuitive, inclusion-sensitive authoring systems that enable both teachers and students to create immersive, accessible learning environments. These systems should be supported by accompanying development guidelines that facilitate co-constructive and participatory design processes. Equally important is deliberately creating time and space within daily school and work routines for connecting didactic goals, materials, and XR content. This can be achieved through interdisciplinary project tracks, partnerships with external organizations, or flexible development labs.

To promote this open ecosystem, public educational actors, research networks, and non-profit organizations

should create targeted incentives, such as research funding, recognition systems, or curriculum integration. This creates an inclusive, resilient, and pedagogically compatible XR ecosystem that serves as a sustainable foundation for digital education in the public interest.

5.3 Securing infrastructure & access to XR technology

The scenario shows how Luca and her classmates work seamlessly with adapted XR devices, regardless of individual requirements or family background. This technical equal opportunity does not emerge automatically but requires systematic measures at the hardware, software, and infrastructure levels.

The development of open-source operating systems for XR devices should be actively promoted. Similar to the Linux distribution model, these systems would enable schools to create, or commission tailored versions for their specific pedagogical and didactic requirements. The currently dominant dependence on proprietary manufacturer systems significantly restricts educational institutions in their design autonomy. Open-source solutions, by contrast, ensure full control over functionality, data protection standards, and the pedagogical orientation of the technology being used. Initial developments in this direction already exist, for example in the form of emerging open or semi-open XR operating system initiatives, which indicate that alternatives to fully proprietary ecosystems are technically feasible even today. For example, initiatives such as Android-based XR platforms¹ or the WebXR Device API² illustrate that open and modular (operating) system concepts for immersive devices are already under development.

The continuous availability of XR devices requires competent maintenance structures directly on-site. Technical support staff at schools should be able to maintain XR devices, keep replacement devices on hand, and provide immediate support when problems arise. In parallel, public provision of these devices by schools and the state is recommended. In this context, XR devices can also be assigned to students as personal loan devices for longer periods of time. Only this approach can prevent XR education from depending on family resources and reinforcing existing inequalities.

At the hardware level, consistently accessible solutions are required: lighter headsets to reduce strain on neck muscles, modular controllers for personalized control, and

² <https://www.android.com/xr>.

³ <https://immersiveweb.dev>.

multimodal interfaces through eye and body tracking. This variety of input options ensures that all learners can use the technology independently according to their individual capabilities.

On the software side, inclusive features should be integral to the design process from the very beginning: automatic captioning, sign language simultaneous translation, adjustable color schemes, and other accessibility features should be implemented as core functions, not as afterthoughts.

5.4 Establishing standards & guidelines for data protection, quality, interfaces & accessibility

The seamless and inclusive XR use depicted in the scenario is based on binding standards that consider data protection, quality, and accessibility as integral elements from the very beginning. Without such frameworks, there is a risk of fragmented isolated solutions that are neither interoperable nor inclusive.

Building on existing discourse in the field of learning analytics, a specific data protection framework for XR educational contexts needs to be developed. The particular sensitivity of body data, such as movement patterns, gaze behavior, and biometric information, requires enhanced protection concepts. Additionally, ethical guidelines are needed to regulate the pedagogically responsible handling of emotionally intensive XR experiences.

For quality assurance, a multi-level system is recommended: educational institutions can award certifications for verified content, while community-based rating systems enable dynamic quality control through user feedback. In parallel, a standardized accessibility score should be developed that makes the accessibility of XR applications measurable using transparent checklists.

Technical standards must ensure interoperability and long-term availability. This includes both metaverse-compatible interfaces for multi-user scenarios and availability guarantees that ensure once-created learning environments remain permanently accessible. Inclusive design must be embedded as a transversal task throughout all development phases, supported by practical checklists, development guidelines, and ongoing awareness that future multisensory, AI-supported, and multimodal innovations must also be designed inclusively.

The entire standardization process must be designed to be interdisciplinary and participatory. Only through the systematic inclusion of educational stakeholders in Communities of Practice can practical standards emerge that connect technical innovation with pedagogical objectives.

These considerations extend existing debates on learning analytics and data protection into the specific context of immersive and embodied learning environments.

5.5 Strengthening professionalization & school development

Building a Community of Practice around XR both within individual schools and across schools is a central measure for leveraging synergies, benefiting from shared ideas, and collaboratively developing best-practice scenarios. These practices can then be disseminated by XR Learning coordinators within schools to their respective teaching faculties, ensuring that less tech-savvy teachers like Alex in the scenario are also involved. Exchange between XR Learning coordinators is also essential for this process. To strengthen school development, internal formats such as classroom observations, collegial feedback, and collaborative content creation can be implemented.

Cross-school access to authoring systems and their didactic use within the Community of Practice helps reduce barriers that could prevent achieving the presented scenario.

Additionally, a comprehensive curriculum should be developed that spans all phases of teacher education. This curriculum should not be viewed as simply a “technology driver’s license,” but rather as a thoughtful approach to developing XR-related competencies where pedagogy remains the guiding principle. To reach the goals outlined in the scenario, teacher professional development in XR should extend beyond technical training to also focus on areas like educational equity, inclusion, and differentiated learning approaches – in addition to pedagogical integration, classroom orchestration, and organizational routines.¹⁷

Part of professionalizing stakeholders requires research that can, for example, support implementation processes, demonstrate evidence for beneficial implementations, and help develop theoretical frameworks. To achieve this effectively, teachers should be involved as active participants in research and development processes.

5.6 Shaping coordination, cooperation & political frameworks

The scenario illustrates what becomes possible when XR technology, pedagogy, and inclusion are systematically aligned with each other. This state can only be achieved through strategic governance and coordinated measures at the educational, technological, and political levels.

A central element is establishing regional and supra-regional XR competence centers that advise schools and teachers, support technical standards, and coordinate exchange formats. These centers could be located at universities or established as inter-university collaborations to connect research, teacher education, and school practice. As interfaces, they also play a role in coordinating with existing infrastructures such as educational clouds and media centers. A shared understanding and terminology are key prerequisites for effective cooperation. Existing community structures – such as the XR-Learning working group^{3F4} in the German Informatics Society (GI), including networking initiatives like uniVERSEty – already provide a starting point for cross-institutional coordination.

For long-term implementation, clear responsibilities for investment, maintenance, and ongoing development are needed. These should be formally established at institutional, municipal, and national levels through measures such as funded positions, support structures, and minimum technical requirements.

Strategic incentive systems are essential. They should not only promote the development of open and accessible XR content but also strengthen local engagement through measures such as compensating the XR coordinators mentioned earlier and providing targeted support for Communities of Practice.

At the same time, coordinated demand must create critical mass against market-dominant providers in order to enforce openness and standards. Funding policy measures should prioritize solutions oriented toward the public good.

A sustainable political framework is essential for making education with immersive media reliable, inclusive, and future-ready. This applies not only to XR but to digital education as a whole: innovation requires structure.

6 Conclusions

Immersive technologies are increasingly gaining importance in the school education context. This article used a normatively oriented scenario method to identify central design requirements and courses of action for their use in schools. Through an interdisciplinary process, experts from education, technology, and inclusion developed a shared target vision, a vivid future scenario, and concrete measures building on these foundations.

The results show three key findings. First, immersive technologies must be designed didactically so that they not

only have motivating and experience-based effects, but are also embedded in curricula, usable for reflection, and capable of addressing diverse learners. Second, it became clear that technological developments should be designed particularly in areas such as interoperable platforms, open standards, and accessible interfaces in order to be compatible and inclusively effective in the long term. Third, the article emphasizes the relevance of a value-oriented perspective: inclusion, participation, transparency, and pedagogical responsibility must be anchored as consistent principles throughout technology development and use. The measures developed therefore address not only concrete implementation steps in teaching, but also structural questions of participation, research, and data stewardship.

Predictions about the future of school education with immersive technologies remain inherently uncertain – technological development is too dynamic and school realities are too heterogeneous. Accordingly, this paper combines different approaches: drawing on existing research, complementing it with expert consensus and scenario-based reasoning, which is consistent with the aim of the special issue. The aim of this article is to develop informed, value-driven visions for the future. To reduce speculative bias, the analysis is grounded in interdisciplinary expertise and limited to a 10-year horizon to balance the plausibility with visionary potential. To sum it up, the paper offers an informed, value-driven and action-oriented roadmap for K-12 XR adoption over the next decade by connecting a concrete classroom scenario with actionable requirements for technology, pedagogy, inclusion, and governance. In doing so, this article can provide impulses for conducting discussions about XR technologies in education in a nuanced, value-conscious, and action-oriented manner. The goal is to help shape a positive, equitable, and pedagogically grounded future for schools where immersive technologies are not ends in themselves but means for promoting successful learning processes for all students.

Future research should empirically investigate how the identified principles – such as inclusive XR design, open infrastructures, and teacher-support systems – are implemented and appropriated in concrete school contexts. In particular, the increasing role of artificial intelligence in immersive learning environments requires systematic examination, including questions of pedagogical transparency, ethical data use, and the balance between adaptive support and teacher autonomy. Beyond technological aspects, further work is needed on governance, standards, and sustainability to ensure that immersive and AI-supported educational technologies develop in an inclusive, transparent, and publicly accountable manner.

⁴ <https://ak-xrl.gi.de>.

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Use of Large Language Models, AI and Machine Learning

Tools: We used generative AI tools (ChatGPT, Gemini) primarily for language-related support, including proofreading and translation into English. Beyond language, AI (ChatGPT, Gemini, NotebookLM) was used as an assisting tool during qualitative synthesis (e.g., to support clustering and summarizing workshop contributions) and to support literature scoping. All AI outputs were critically reviewed by the authors. Empirical interpretations and the final synthesis were authored by the research team, who take full responsibility for the manuscript.

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